

DATA ARTICLE **OPEN ACCESS**

Facilitating Effective Reuse of Soil Research Data: The BonaRes Repository

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ABSTRACT

Soil plays a paramount role in addressing complex challenges related to climate change, the agri-food system, and ecosystem services. This importance makes soil research data highly relevant for meta-analysis, research synthesis, modelling, and assessment. As data-intensive techniques proliferate in studying global change impacts on agricultural systems, effective data management and reuse are essential. Repositories that adhere to the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles are crucial for maximizing the value and efficiency of research data. While publishing in an Open Access repository is necessary for data reusability, it alone is not sufficient. Specialized repositories enhance data reuse potential by addressing discipline-specific needs through targeted metadata and technical frameworks. The BonaRes Repository was developed for agricultural soil research data and is guided by the FAIR principles, with a focus on data reusability. Here, we introduce the repository's infrastructures and services, including specialized tools for data quality assurance and the management of soil profile as well as long-term field experiment data. We emphasize the ability of these infrastructures and services to promote data publication and reuse specifically in soil and agricultural sciences. We review examples of data reuse, highlighting their scientific contributions to the understanding of soil and agricultural systems. Finally, we discuss the remaining challenges in achieving FAIR and open soil data publication and reusability. From 2018 to date, the BonaRes Repository has facilitated 815 data publications; 62 papers have reused the published data. Reuse applications range widely—from extracting study site metadata or environmental covariates to reanalysing (meta)data in light of new research questions, to developing scenarios and conducting model calibration and evaluation. A key insight from our review of data reuse is that researchers frequently apply reused data to advance method development. Initiatives such as reciprocal metadata harvesting and integration into larger national and international research data infrastructure will further expand the scope and reuse of the repository's data, including in broader agrosystems science.

1 | Introduction

Global soil and agricultural systems increasingly face societal and environmental challenges, requiring evidence-based

solutions to sustain ecosystem services and crop and livestock production for future generations (Bahim et al. 2020). Soils play a crucial role in managing agricultural systems and ecosystem services under global change. As such, soil science is a key

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Summary

- The BonaRes Repository provides core as well as specialized infrastructures and services that support FAIR publication and reuse of agricultural soil research data.
- To date, the BonaRes Repository has published 815 datasets, with 62 papers reusing 60 unique datasets.
- Applications of reused data span a wide range, from metadata extraction to scenario development and model calibration. Reused data are frequently applied in method development and evaluation.
- Integration with national and international research data infrastructure expands the repository's scope and reuse across agrosystems science.

field for the application of systematic reviews, meta-analyses, modelling, and other integrative approaches towards scientific assessment and synthesis (Halpern et al. 2020; Collins 2020). The advancement of data-driven technologies and Artificial Intelligence further increases the demand for reliable data infrastructures to enhance scientific data reuse (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Ali and Dahlhaus 2022; Gries et al. 2023).

The FAIR data principles were created by stakeholders (academia, industry, funding agencies, and publishers) to help researchers make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Boeckhout et al. 2018). Many international (e.g., Research Data Alliance [RDA]) and national (e.g., Berlin Declaration on Open Access, 2003, openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration) initiatives have promoted FAIR data publishing practices. Funding agencies are pushing to increase the scientific and societal value of their investments with initiatives from North American funders (e.g., NSF (nsf.gov), USGS (usgs.gov)) or the European Union HORIZON programme (<http://ec.europa.eu/research/eic>, Bahim et al. 2020; Stendal et al. 2023). Additionally, publishers necessitate data publication to promote open science and ensure transparency for journal reviewers (Nosek et al. 2015; Kinkade and Shepherd 2022).

Importantly, data discovery and reusability are not guaranteed through publication in Open Access repositories (Roche et al. 2015; Husen et al. 2017) but are rather enhanced by specialized repositories (Hampton et al. 2013; Khan et al. 2022) focused on discipline-specific needs, meta-data and technical frameworks (Kahn et al. 2016; Kinkade and Shepherd 2022; Gries et al. 2023). Specialized repositories offer standardized, rich, and well-curated metadata along with targeted search portals optimized for community-specific data types to increase data findability and accessibility (Chong et al. 2024). Reusability requires provenance documentation, proper licensing and persistent digital identifiers for data and metadata. Linking dataset and metadata attributes to terms in standardized community-endorsed ontologies are crucial for data interoperability and reuse (Chong et al. 2024). Specialized repositories often apply strict quality controls, another key factor driving data reuse (Khan et al. 2022; Russell 2025), and offer data steward support and educational resources on FAIR practices and research

data management (Borghini and Van Gulick 2021; Kinkade and Shepherd 2022).

Research in soil and agricultural sciences draws upon multiple data sources, including data from controlled field trials, analytical chemistry of soil properties, plant phenotypic measurements, environmental monitoring networks, socio-economic surveys, predictive models, satellite imagery, and geographic information databases (Senft et al. 2022). For most agricultural research studies, physical, biological, and chemical soil properties, soil classifications, and/or soil quality assessments are indispensable base information traditionally gathered from soil profiles. Similarly, data from long-term field experiments (LTEs) are particularly valuable for soil-agricultural science due to the slow nature of soil adaptation to changing conditions (Barkusky 2009; Grosse et al. 2020; Grosse 2021). However, a significant amount of soil profile and LTE (meta)data, collected over decades, are neither publicly documented nor published, making them non-reusable despite their great relevance, particularly in relation to ongoing climatic changes. This gap necessitated the development of specialized and standardized data publication infrastructures for soil profile and LTE data.

Geospatial data are increasingly published in spatial data infrastructures (SDI) (Trilles et al. 2017; Simmons 2018; Stein et al. 2019). The European Union's INSPIRE directive (EU 2007) has been the driving force in the development of SDIs in Europe including the Spatial Data Infrastructure Germany (GDI-DE, www.gdi-de.org/en), which openly provides digital soil maps of Germany at different scales. Internationally, there are national governmental initiatives such as by the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) and the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS, www.nrcs.usda.gov/wps/portal/nrcs/site/soils/home), which host U.S. soil surveys (Schaefer et al. 2007). In Australia, the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO, csiro.au/en/research/natural-environment/land/soil-and-landscape-grid-of-australia) administers gridded soil data (Johnston et al. 2003). In Europe, France maintains the National Soil Data Centre (Richer-de-Forges and Arrouays 2010), the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC, esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu) manages soil-related data for the European Commission and beyond (Panagos et al. 2022), while the ISRIC Soil Metadata catalogue (www.isric.org/isric-metadata-catalogue) and ISRIC SoilGrids (Poggio et al. 2021) and WoSIS portal (Batjes et al. 2024) as part of the ISRIC World Data Centre for Soils host soil property maps and accept submissions of soil profile data. Even more specialized are the International Soil Carbon Network (iscn.fluxdata.org/about-iscn) and Edaphobase—a data warehouse for soil biodiversity (Burkhardt et al. 2014; Russell et al. 2024) lately expanded to the European level as EUdaphobase (www.eudaphobase.eu). Moreover, there are repositories from related disciplines that, among others, manage agricultural research data, such as PANGAEA (www.pangaea.de, Felden et al. 2023) for earth system research, the open access repository OpenAgrar (www.openagrar.de), or the electronic data archive library for plant genomics and phenomics eDAL-PGP (edal-pgp.ipk-gatersleben.de, Arend et al. 2016).

Here, we present the BonaRes Repository (www.bonares.de/research-data), which addresses the remaining lack of specialized SDIs for publishing and reusing geospatial soil-agricultural research data. The repository was established in 2016 as part of the BonaRes research program in soil science and sustainable agriculture (Vogel et al. 2018; Techen et al. 2020), funded by the German Federal Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF, www.bmbf.de/EN). The BonaRes Repository continues to serve as a platform for soil science data publication, operating as a persistent institutional core infrastructure of the Leibniz Center for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF, www.zalf.de/en). To reflect on the BonaRes Repository's impact and to promote FAIR data practices in agricultural soil research, our discussion unfolds as follows: First, we introduce the repository's general infrastructures and services, highlighting their advantages for data authors and reusers. Second, we present the specialized infrastructures for publishing LTE and soil profile (meta)data, emphasizing how they align with the needs of the soil science community and complement existing SDIs. Third, we review examples of data reuse from the repository, including their scientific contributions to our understanding of soil and agricultural systems. Finally, we discuss the remaining challenges on the path towards FAIR and open soil data publication and reusability, providing perspectives on ongoing research data management (RDM) initiatives.

2 | The BonaRes Repository

The BonaRes Repository strives to fully implement the FAIR principles for publishing soil and agricultural research data from both German and international sources. The repository publishes all data formats relevant to the soil science

community. These include structured tabular datasets (CSV, Excel) to geospatial files (GeoTIFF, shapefile), time series, imagery, unstructured text, and complex relational databases (e.g., LTE data) requiring specialized data management approaches. To this end, the repository offers comprehensive services and tools that support users from data processing through publication to reuse (Figure 1). At its core, the repository maintains SDI and long-term archiving infrastructures (Section 2.1, Figure 1—centre), while institutional and project-funded data stewards at ZALF assist data authors with various aspects of data publication (Sections 2.1 and 2.2, Figure 1—bottom). Data steward services range from assistance with (meta)data preparation to ensuring legal compliance. Complementary discipline-specific services have been developed to enhance data processing and reuse, including tailored solutions for LTE and soil profile data publication (Section 2.2, Figure 1—correspondingly coloured fields left and right). Below, we detail the infrastructures and services shown in Figure 1, emphasizing how they support data authors and reusers from agricultural soil sciences throughout the data life cycle.

2.1 | Infrastructure and Services

The BonaRes Repository's core data infrastructure (Figure 1, centre) is a spatial data infrastructure (SDI) following the 'Open Geospatial Consortium' (OGC) standards (www.ogc.org/publications), ensuring interoperability with existing national and international SDIs, such as the SDI Germany (GDI-DE, www.geoportal.de) or the European Commission's INSPIRE Geoportal (inspire-geoportal.ec.europa.eu). Data stewards bridge infrastructure and data authors by verifying metadata structure, content, and technical conformity. Connected within

FIGURE 1 | Core (grey) and discipline-specific (coloured circles) infrastructures and services of the BonaRes Repository (www.bonares.de/research-data).

the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) and research community, they provide consultations on data management plans and offer workshops and training sessions.

The repository provides a secure storage infrastructure as well as long-term archiving (LTA) for diverse data types, preferring non-proprietary formats to enable archiving and reuse. The digital LTA system incorporates an automatic workflow with feedback, bitstream and semantic preservation, format migration, and data replication. Through a contract with ZB MED (www.zbmed.de/en), data is stored indefinitely at both ZALF and in a secure 'dark archive' that is not publicly accessible.

Policies established at the BonaRes Repository (Svoboda and Heinrich 2017; Svoboda 2021; Svoboda et al. 2024) and ZALF (2023) detail guidelines for data handling, including optional temporary embargo periods, submission deadlines, and licensing. They also cover citation rules, protocols for handling versioning and withdrawal, and procedures for assigning Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) and Creative Commons (creativecommons.org) licences to data. All data published in the repository are subject to the CC-BY licence, which balances free reuse and benefit for the authors. Metadata receive the CC0 licence. The licences are stored as machine-readable metadata elements and are displayed in the repository in human-readable form. Customized policies can be developed upon request to accommodate specific project requirements.

2.2 | Discipline Specific Data Services

In addition to its core data publication infrastructure, the BonaRes Repository offers the following specialized data services: (1) The Upload-Tool and geo-spatial search interface for data download (blue in Figure 1); (2) The BonaRes Metadata Schema compatible with national and international Spatial Data Infrastructures (blue-green); (3) The DQ-Kit, enabling researchers to assess data quality (cream); (4) The Soil Profile Database, a dedicated service for publishing soil profile data (beige-brown); (5) The LTE Overview Map, providing information on long-term field experiments (LTEs) across Europe (brown). These five services support both data processing and reuse (Figure 1).

2.2.1 | Data Upload, Publication and Download

Upload. Data submissions to the repository are facilitated through the Upload Tool (tools.dataservice.zalf.de/submission), a web application designed for submitting both data and metadata and enabling the data authors to track the progress of their data publication. Prior registration is required. Data stewards assist in particular with metadata editing.

Publication. In the data publication process, data stewards review the submissions to evaluate the data and metadata organization (completeness, conformity, clarity, etc.) and technical conformity. This review is essential for ensuring the reusability of research data, which relies on having comprehensive and well-structured metadata (see also Section 2.2.2). Connecting spatial data to the standardized OGC Web Map Services (WMS) enhances data interoperability by enabling integration into GIS

systems for advanced analysis. Once the review is successfully completed, the research data are published in the BonaRes Repository with a DOI and CC licence.

Download. The BonaRes Repository is a search interface that enables advanced geo-search capabilities, tailored to landscape-oriented research. A targeted search using keywords from the European GEMET (www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/about) and the international AGROVOC (www.fao.org/agrovoc) Thesauri is supported. All published data can also be found via Google's Dataset Search (datasetsearch.research.google.com). For download, data re-users can choose from a variety of data formats and coordinate systems, and receive a download link via email—typically within minutes—once data has been prepared with their chosen properties. This approach enhances interoperability and accommodates the diverse standards of different landscape research disciplines.

2.2.2 | Metadata Services

Interoperability. The BonaRes Metadata Schema (Gärtner et al. 2017; Specka et al. 2019) ensures cross-portal metadata interoperability with other national and international SDIs through adherence to the INSPIRE (EU 2007) and DataCite (datacite.org) metadata standards as well as standards for network services and data specifications. The OGC standardized SDI enables access to geodata via OGC web map services (OGC WMS) (Hoffmann et al. 2020). Additionally, metadata are provided in a Schema.org format for integration with Google Dataset Search and the FAIRagro (fairagro.net) network of research data infrastructures (Specka et al. 2019; García Brizuela et al. 2024). The BonaRes Metadata Schema includes elements beyond those found in the INSPIRE or DataCite metadata models enhancing reusability. These elements allow for a detailed description of tabular data including methods, units, provenance, and data relationships. We use the community endorsed AGROVOC and GEMET Thesauri providing consistent keywords for dataset annotation. AGROVOC is a multilingual agricultural Thesaurus managed by the Food Agricultural Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, making the annotated data easier to find and reuse across international research communities. Clear measurement definitions are essential for data interoperability and reuse (Chong et al. 2024). Varied definitions across agricultural and soil science disciplines can hinder interpretation and synthesis (Ma and Gali-Izard 2023; Batjes et al. 2024).

Legal compliance. The BonaRes Metadata Schema incorporates elements for Digital Object Identifier (DOI) registration and professional licence disclaimers. Assigning DOIs to data through DataCite makes data easier to find, cite, and credit in future research (Svoboda et al. 2024). Creative Commons (CC) licences have been established as standard in the BonaRes Repository, with CC-BY applied to data and CC0 to metadata. Together with the DOI, adequate licensing is a prerequisite for legally compliant data citations and reuse (Kinkade and Shepherd 2022; Khan et al. 2022).

Metadata harvesting. The BonaRes Repository not only hosts original research data but also harvests standardized and machine-actionable metadata from other repositories, such

as Edaphobase (Burkhardt et al. 2014). By linking to the original data via their persistent identifier (PID), harvesting enhances data discoverability. As of March 2025, more than 4000 datasets from other infrastructures have been findable in the BonaRes Repository search through metadata harvesting. Reciprocally, other initiatives, such as EOSC (eosc.eu) and the European Soil Observatory (joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/eu-soil-observatory-euso_en), FAIRagro or Google Dataset Search can harvest metadata from the BonaRes Repository using defined and standardized interfaces like CSW and Schema.org. Metadata harvesting via OGC CSW automates the retrieval and integration of geospatial metadata from distributed repositories using a standardized API for querying and synchronization in formats like ISO 19115/19139. This approach enhances soil science data discoverability and reusability across platforms.

2.2.3 | DQ-Kit: Data Quality Assessment Tool

Data quality plays a crucial role in promoting data reuse (Wiser 2016; Khan et al. 2022) and the success of data-driven methods and technologies (Clemente et al. 2023). Issues such as unbalanced or poorly represented data, insufficient sample sizes, data gaps, redundant information, and data inconsistencies can potentially undermine the assumptions of statistical analyses (Chen et al. 2014; Clemente et al. 2023). The BonaRes repository's DQ-Kit (dqkit.bonares.de) has been developed with dual objectives: to assist authors in assessing the quality of their data prior to publication, and to enable data reusers to evaluate the reusability of previously published data for their specific research questions. The free online tool provides statistical and graphical data exploration as well as automated guidance on data elements that need review and confirmation as implemented in the Python library *YData profiling* (Clemente et al. 2023). DQ-Kit's downloadable HTML report includes: (1) a dataset overview; (2) summary statistics at the variable level (including, e.g., histograms); (3) exploration of variable associations (e.g., pairwise correlations, scatterplots); and (4) data quality alerts of variable properties that might require consideration (e.g., skewness, collinearity). The variable level summary statistics (histogram, quantiles and lists of extreme values) support the identification of outliers. Importantly, DQ-Kit does not modify the data, nor is there a routine involvement of reviewers or data stewards. The responsibility for handling the results and alerts provided lies with the data author, who has the final authority in determining their validity. Similarly, DQ-Kit enables re-users to self-responsibly assess data suitability for their particular needs. The DQ-Kit report can be submitted as a supplement to data submissions at the BonaRes Repository.

2.2.4 | Soil Profile Database

Traditionally, soil profiles or soil cores have been used for soil classification and soil development studies (Hartemink and Minasny 2014). Horizon description characterizes soil genesis and structure providing standardized information on features such as soil colour (Kirillova et al. 2018) as well as physical (e.g., soil aggregation, texture, moisture, and air) (Iversen et al. 2001) and chemical constitution (redox reactions, composition and

displacement of minerals) (Chadwick and Chorover 2001; Zhang and Furman 2021). However, the recording of soil profile information follows mainly national standards such as KA5 in Germany (Sponagel et al. 2005), USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service in the USA (Soil Survey Staff 2024), the *Référentiel pédologique* in France (Baize and Girard 2009) or, on an international scale, the FAO Guideline for Soil Description (FAO 2006) and is often still documented in field books or locally in digital storage with limited accessibility (Campbell et al. 2017).

In Germany, government-collected soil profiles are managed and published in a standardized manner at the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (FISBo BGR, www.bgr.bund.de/EN). Based on the existing BGR database schema, the BonaRes Repository's Soil Profile Database (tools.bonares.de/bp_db/map) makes previously inaccessible soil profile data from research projects available in one place (Figure 2). This online tool enables the publication of standardized soil profile data in accordance with the German Soil Survey Guidelines in different editions (KA3–KA5, Sponagel et al. 2005). Researchers can input data either from existing datasets or directly via the digital form during fieldwork. After a review by the repository's data stewards—who assess the completeness of metadata such as titles, descriptions, and authors, as well as the plausibility of the provided geographic information—soil profiles are published and assigned a DOI through DataCite, ensuring that published soil profiles are citable and easily referenced. Individual profiles can be grouped into collections (e.g., by soil types or regions) and cited in subsequent studies. With the spatial location of the soil profile being a mandatory entry, the Soil Profile Database offers significant potential for aggregating valuable, structured, and standardized soil data and making it visible and widely accessible for soil research. The Soil Profile Database is the latest addition to the BonaRes Repository, containing 51 profiles as of mid-March 2025, with more profiles planned for future inclusion.

2.2.5 | LTE Database Schema and Overview Map

Agricultural long-term field experiments (LTEs) provide consistent and reliable data over extended periods of time, enabling researchers to distinguish between short-term responses and long-term effects of different farming (e.g., crop rotation), soil management practices, and global change on agricultural soil health, crop yield, and sustainability (Bybee-Finley et al. 2024). LTE data may also serve to develop and test new hypotheses, concepts, and models, as well as to achieve synthesis on pressing questions (Patel et al. 2021). Consequently, at the BonaRes Repository, a specific mandatory database schema has been designed for LTEs (Kühnert et al. 2024). This standardized database structure enhances harmonization of LTE data across experiments and thus reusability, integration and comparability. LTE data quality is assured by rules and constraints that enforce consistency and validity in data entries.

The LTE Overview Map (tools.bonares.de/lte), established in 2017 for German LTEs, is an integral component of the BonaRes Repository, now serving as a comprehensive information tool for LTEs across Europe and beyond enhancing their impact

FIGURE 2 | Workflow of soil profile data publication. Submission of field and legacy soil profile data to the Soil Profile Database (https://tools.bonares.de/bp_db/map/), review, publication and re-use processes.

through data sharing, collaboration, and reuse. Metadata from numerous LTEs worldwide has been collected through an extensive bibliographic review and personal communication with LTE holders to ensure a comprehensive and diverse LTE dataset. Additionally, the map integrates metadata from various international networks, including EJP SOIL (ejpsoil.eu), GLTEN (glten.org), ILTER (ilter.network), IOSDV (International Organic Nitrogen Long-Term Field Experiments), and others, providing a centralized platform for accessing and exploring LTE metadata. Notably, Dönmez et al. (2022a, 2022b) identified 616 different LTEs across Europe with a lifetime varying from 20 to 141 years. The metadata of those and an additional four European LTEs are featured in the LTE Overview Map as of March 2025.

As a core feature, the LTE Overview Map facilitates the standardization and harmonization of LTE metadata. To collect LTE metadata directly from LTE holders, a tabular fact sheet template has been developed for gathering comprehensive standardized meta-information on, for instance, research theme, the experimental design, site details, measured parameters, and sampling procedures (see Grosse et al. (2019) for an example). To ensure that the LTEs are well-presented, we expect at least the following fields to be provided: location, start date, status, country, land use, farming category, site name, and, if possible, the holding institution for the trial. The template allows data providers to select predefined parameters analysed in their trial but also to add custom parameters in blank rows. The collected metadata is reviewed and integrated into the LTE map by data stewards and researchers of the BonaRes Repository. Reusers can easily filter and locate specific LTEs based on criteria such as fertilization, tillage, and crop types. The map's functionality

extends beyond mere information provision and visualization. It allows users to download detailed metadata for each LTE in PDF format, enabling scientists to quickly assess the relevance and potential of specific LTEs for their studies. As such, the LTE Overview enhances the BonaRes Repository's value as a research data infrastructure, significantly contributing to data reuse by making structured LTE (meta)data readily accessible and reusable.

3 | From Publication to Reuse: Evaluating the Impact of BonaRes Repository Data

Data reusability enhances research value and efficiency while increasing author visibility. Beyond findability and accessibility, true reusability requires additional efforts (Roche et al. 2015; Husen et al. 2017). The discipline-specific infrastructures and services of the BonaRes Repository are specifically tailored to facilitating the FAIR principles and data reuse. In the following, we evaluate how the repository has so far advanced the publication and reuse of agricultural soil research data.

3.1 | Repository Use Statistics

From its founding to date, the number of annual data publications in the BonaRes Repository has grown from 48 in 2018 to 170 in 2023. For 2024, we recorded 169 and for 2025 so far 28 completed publications, with more additions underway (Figure 3). Cumulatively, there have been 815 data publications, with 723 assigned DOIs (note that multiple related datasets are often published as data collection under one

FIGURE 3 | Publication statistics of the BonaRes Repository as of 13 March 2025. The figure shows the number of datasets published, Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) assigned, datasets downloaded, and publications reusing datasets since the repository's inception. Bars show individual counts per year while lines indicate cumulative numbers.

DOI). Data downloads have also increased consistently, peaking at 1158 in 2024. To date, we have recorded a total of 3974 downloads.

We have undertaken a comprehensive effort to identify instances of data reuse, including metadata reuse and subsequent uses by the research teams that initially submitted the datasets, while excluding papers directly associated with the initial submission. We conducted searches on Google Scholar and Scopus using the DOI components ALL (10.4228/zalf) and ALL (10.20387/bonares) as search terms. Additionally, we searched for ALL (lte.bonares.de), ALL (tools.bonares.de), ALL (bonares.de/research-data), and ALL (maps.bonares.de/mapapps/resources/apps/bonares/index.html?) to find citations of our services. Notably, the ISI Web of Science (WoS) search does not include the relevant paper sections 'Main Text', 'Data Availability Statement' and 'References' and thus did not yield any results. Cumulative dissertations that contained only previously considered publications were excluded. We identified 62 unique publications that reused 60 unique datasets and documented the types and purposes of data reuse (Table S1). Applications of data reuse (Figure 4, Table S1) range from extracting study site metadata and environmental covariates, through (re-)analysis of (meta)data to answer new research questions, to scenario development, calibration, and evaluation in crop yield and agro-ecosystem modelling studies.

To provide a systematic overview of the scientific objectives addressed by publications reusing data from the BonaRes

FIGURE 4 | Bar plot of data reuse type as recorded in Table S1. More than one reuse type is possible for each reuse of a dataset. If a publication reused more than one dataset, each data set has been considered separately.

Repository, we conducted bibliometric analyses using R (version 4.4.1, R Core Team 2024) for the subset of 46 publications also listed in WoS (see Table S1). First, we used the R package *bibliometrix* (Aria and Cuccurullo 2017) on full BibTex records from WoS to produce a Sankey diagram of author country, ISI Discipline and ISI keywords (Figure 5), except for two publications lacking ISI keywords. Due to the repository's origins at a German institution and its association with the German BonaRes program, the majority of data reusers are from Germany (AU_CO). However, international collaborations with European countries and beyond are also evident. Data reuse occurred primarily in soil-related disciplines (SC) such as agriculture, ecological sciences, and geology, but also extended to more distantly related fields like imaging science and economics. The identified keywords (ID) highlight global change and sustainability-related issues (e.g., climate change, ecosystem services, and biodiversity) and modelling studies (e.g., uncertainty, dynamics, and model).

Next, for keyword analysis in *litsearchr* (Grames et al. 2019, 2020), we extracted author keywords from the WoS records and identified additional important keywords occurring in titles and abstracts applying a simplified Rapid Automatic Keyword Extraction algorithm (RAKE, Rose et al. 2010). We allowed a keyword length between two and three words, excluded terms occurring less than twice, and used a stopwords list (see provided R code, Lachmuth et al. 2025) to avoid common terms lacking scientific relevance. We combined author and RAKE keywords (115 unique keywords) to perform a network analysis of keywords co-occurring in the publications' titles, abstracts, and author keywords merging terms such as singular and plural forms of the same term (see Table S2). Here, the agricultural context, agricultural (long-term) field experiments, abiotic conditions and ecology, but also methodological topics related to (crop) modelling and remote sensing form key topics of data reuse (Figure 6).

3.2 | BonaRes Data Reuse Contributes to Agricultural and Soil Science

The reuse of the repository's comprehensive and accessible database has enabled diverse research applications

FIGURE 5 | Three-Field Sankey Diagram created using the R package *bibliometrix*, illustrating the connections between Author Country (all authors, AU), Web of Science Subject Category (SC), and Web of Science Keywords (ID). This visualization includes 44 of the 62 papers that reused data from the BonaRes Repository, specifically those listed in ISI Web of Science (WoS) with associated WoS keywords (see Table S1).

(Figures 3–6) supporting, for instance, studies on climate change impacts and the optimization of agricultural practices. The documented data reuse spans the soil science community, encompassing our own research, data exchange within the BonaRes program, and independent studies. Reused data has proven particularly valuable for advancing methodological approaches across several areas: (meta)data processing (Blanchy, Albrecht, Bragato, et al. 2023; Blanchy, Albrecht, Koestel, et al. 2023), laboratory analysis (Reyes and Ließ 2022), data analytics (Thai, Bellingrath-Kimura, et al. 2020; Thai, Omari, et al. 2020; Ingwersen et al. 2024), and modelling techniques (Zare et al. 2022; Schäfer Rodrigues Silva et al. 2022; Zare, Weber, et al. 2024; Zare, Viswanathan, et al. 2024; Attia et al. 2024). Next, we examine three data reuse case clusters: the LTE map initiative at the BonaRes Repository, collaborative data reuse within an agroforestry research project, and the reuse of a comprehensive soil–vegetation and land surface processes data publication by Weber et al. (2022), which was not part of BonaRes. These examples demonstrate the research benefits of data reuse.

3.2.1 | LTE Data: A Valuable Resource for Climate Impact and Yield Studies

The LTE Overview Map initiative (see Section 2.2.5) has already stimulated various research efforts, enabling spatial modelling and classification techniques (Grosse et al. 2020; Dönmez et al. 2024), studies of climate change impacts on soils and agriculture (Dönmez et al. 2023) and a comprehensive review of LTE operations (Dönmez et al. 2022a; Blanchy et al. 2024). Dönmez et al. (2023) quantified the expected, spatially differentiated changes in agroclimatic conditions for the German LTE sites to support modelling and LTE data interpretation. They utilized extensive metadata from 247 LTE sites, stored in the BonaRes Repository. A GIS-based framework was implemented to integrate spatially distributed climate data with LTE metadata, identifying potential climatic changes at LTE sites under the IPCC's Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSP, IPCC (2021)). This framework facilitated enhanced modelling and interpretation of agroclimatic conditions, highlighting the repository's crucial role in providing

FIGURE 6 | Network graph of keyword analysis, combining author-provided and RAKE-extracted keywords (generated using the R package *lit-searchr*). This visualization includes 46 of the 62 papers that reused data from the BonaRes Repository, specifically those listed in ISI Web of Science (see Table S1). Closely related, that is, co-occurring terms representing key topics are positioned near each other and are connected by darker lines, while peripheral terms, connecting with faint lines, indicate less related concepts.

FIGURE 7 | Workflow of a reuse showcase of Long-Term Experiment (LTE) metadata and research data from the BonaRes Repository and LTE Overview Map to support spatial modelling. LTE data, combined with ancillary inputs, are used for model calibration and validation, resulting in spatially distributed outputs leading to a scientific publication (modified from Dönmez et al. 2024; CC BY 4.0).

data for climate impact assessments while ensuring research reliability.

The repository's crucial role in providing quality data for model calibration and validation in agricultural studies was demonstrated through research on net primary productivity (NPP) changes at 271 LTE sites in Germany (Dönmez et al. 2024) (Figure 7). Comprehensive spatial data on land use, soil characteristics, and LTE metadata from the repository were utilized in a biogeochemical model to project future productivity at German LTEs. The model results were validated using available research datasets from the BonaRes Repository (Schmidt et al. 2020).

In another LTE data reuse case, the collection of individual metadata was expanded by an agreement between BonaRes and EJP SOIL, creating an extensive database of over 600 LTEs' metadata in Europe (Dönmez et al. 2022a, 2022b). This dataset includes LTEs and other shorter-running experiments and is stored in the BonaRes Repository. The collected attributes were analysed according to several research themes, including fertilization, crop rotation, and tillage treatments. Another recent case study made detailed metadata from mid- and LTEs across Europe accessible, enabling users to explore specific agricultural practices and conditions (Blanchy et al. 2022). This extensive metadataset is housed in the BonaRes Repository and has been reused in a research study

(Blanchy et al. 2024) to analyse LTEs across different pedo-climatic conditions. Both efforts demonstrated how the repository facilitates data collection and sharing, enabling research on specific agricultural practices and environmental contexts and providing valuable metadata to decision-makers, scientists and the public.

3.2.2 | Coordinated Research Design and Data Management Enable Interdisciplinary Synthesis on Agroforestry Systems

The BonaRes Signal project ('Sustainable intensification of agriculture through agroforestry', signal.uni-goettingen.de) demonstrates an effective approach to research data management and reuse. The project assessed ecological, economic, and social benefits of temperate alley-cropping agroforestry versus conventional land use, implementing a coordinated strategy that focused on collaborative data management, quality assurance, and publication in the BonaRes Repository (personal communication). The approach included a common plot design (Schmidt, Swieter, et al. 2019), coordinated data collection over several years, coordinated data processing, and common standards (e.g., units, codes). This interdisciplinary effort integrated soil science, meteorology, and plant pathogen genetics standardizing measurements across three cropland and two grassland sites. This approach facilitated meta-analysis and synthesis resulting in a high-impact publication (Veldkamp et al. 2023) reusing overall 13 datasets previously published in the BonaRes Repository (see Table S1). This meta-analysis of 47 cropland and 16 grassland indicators of ecosystem functions showed that cropland agroforestry enhanced carbon sequestration, habitat for soil biological activity, and wind erosion resistance, while grassland agroforestry improved only carbon sequestration. These alley-cropping benefits occurred without reducing crop yield, grass biomass, or other ecosystem function indicators. More data reuse occurred within the SIGNAL project. Beule and Karlovsky (2021) reused spatial references from Schmidt, Swieter, et al. (2019) for microbial community studies; Beuschel et al. (2020) cited biomass data from Schmidt, Göbel, et al. (2019); and Sutterlütti et al. (2023) and others repurposed Göbel (2018) soil data for grassland growth and evapotranspiration studies, demonstrating how collaborative data management enhances research credibility.

3.2.3 | A Comprehensive Multi-Site, Multi-Crop Data Publication Initiates Crop Modelling Advancements

A comprehensive dataset collection characterizing soil-vegetation and land surface processes in two southwest German regions with contrasting climates was published by Weber et al. (2021) in the BonaRes Repository, accompanied by a publication in the journal *Earth System Science Data* (Weber et al. 2022). The data collection covers 54 site-years (i.e., 2 regions × 3 fields × 9 cropping seasons [2009–2018]), measuring fluxes of water, energy, and carbon dioxide between land and atmosphere at half-hourly intervals. Additionally, it includes diverse crop-related data such as phenological development stages, canopy height, leaf area index, and biomass information. Soil data include time-series of temperature and moisture at various

soil depths, as well as ground heat fluxes, carbon and nitrogen contents. The data have since been reused not only in publications by the original collaborators (Zare et al. 2022; Schäfer Rodrigues Silva et al. 2022; Zare, Weber, et al. 2024; Ingwersen et al. 2024; Zare, Viswanathan, et al. 2024) but also by external researchers (Scheiffele et al. 2024; Attia et al. 2024).

Ingwersen et al. (2024) propose a new method for calculating Net Ecosystem Carbon Balances (or Net Biome Productivity). Using Weber et al.'s data, they show that including harvest residues is essential for accurately assessing cropland source-sink status. Schäfer Rodrigues Silva et al. (2022) developed methods to estimate model similarity for ensemble selection in crop yield modelling, demonstrating how ensembles improve prediction accuracy and help estimate conceptual uncertainty. Similarly, Zare, Weber, et al. (2024) used a multi-model ensemble to show how remote sensing data assimilation enhances predictive performance. For both, the Weber data played a crucial role in model calibration and validation. Two further studies focused on optimizing and evaluating crop-yield model data assimilation using the Weber data: Zare et al. (2022) developed a method for early forecasting of winter wheat yields and analyses of Zare, Viswanathan, et al. (2024) focused on improving yield predictions by accounting for uncertainty in model parameters and weather predictions. Each of these methodological studies also made significant contributions to soil and agricultural research.

Attia et al. (2024), who had not co-authored the Weber et al. (2021, 2022) data publication, reused the data with a primary focus on evaluating the effects of cover cropping and crop rotation on crop yields and soil organic carbon. They reused weather, soil and crop measurement data to parametrise and evaluate a process-based agroecosystems model and farmer reports of agronomic practices to define business as usual scenarios. The results emphasized the potential benefits of implementing cover cropping and diverse crop rotations. Scheiffele et al. (2024) independently used field-scale soil moisture data from Weber et al. (2021) to overcome limitations of hydrological models.

4 | Challenges and Perspectives for Enhancing Data Publication and Reuse

Despite researchers valuing transparency and openness in science (Khan et al. 2022)—including data sharing and reuse (Kinkade and Shepherd 2022; Khan et al. 2022)—a gap persists between this mindset and data publishing practices (Nosek et al. 2015). This is often due to insufficient incentives, such as effective reuse and citation tracing. Data repositories face challenges in implementing effective citation tracing including incorrect dataset citations (i.e., not providing a complete reference with DOI) and difficulties tracking citations in [Supporting Information](#). Moreover, services such as Google Dataset Search have not yet implemented citation tracking. The BonaRes Repository beyond its educational efforts has initiated collaboration with ORCID (orcid.org) for improved traceability. Globally, interoperability between journal systems and data repositories is crucial for automating data citation tracking and a better understanding of data reuse (Khan et al. 2022). Nevertheless, FAIR data publication benefits data holders in several ways. Papers with published data receive more citations than those without (Wallis et al. 2013).

Data publication eliminates responding to individual requests, attracts collaborators (Boland et al. 2017), and ensures long-term preservation (Wiser 2016). Institutional cultural change needs to elevate data publication (Senft et al. 2022) by establishing RDM services ideally with embedded data stewards (Jetten et al. 2021; Arend et al. 2022), providing RDM education, and promoting discipline-specific repositories. Research Data Infrastructures (RDIs) require further conceptual and technical integration and interoperability between specialized repositories and connecting higher-level infrastructures (Khan et al. 2022). This integration is a key goal of Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, nfdi.de) (Hartl et al. 2021). The BonaRes Repository since 2023 forms part of the NFDI FAIRagro consortium (Specka et al. 2023), a community-driven initiative establishing an interoperable and scalable RDI for agrosystem sciences (García Brizuela et al. 2024). The repository is currently migrating to the open-source system GeoNode (geonode.org), a modern technology stack that enhances functionality, usability, and geospatial data capabilities. ZALF coordinates similar efforts of German institutions synchronizing GeoNode's further development, maximizing benefits from joint advancements, and ensuring compliance with FAIR principles. Much emphasis is placed on evaluating community needs concerning data and metadata quality checks and indicators—including for LTEs—and developing procedures to assess 'fit-for-purpose' data quality (Gedicke et al. 2024; Uhlott and Möller 2024). The consortium provides a comprehensive support system through a Data Steward Service Center (fairagro.net/en/helpdesk) and Portal (fairagro.net/en/about-us/our-mission), facilitating knowledge exchange, technology transfer, participatory processes, and legal guidance; FAIRagro aims at contributing to and leading European and international developments in RDI for agrosystem research.

5 | Conclusions

The BonaRes Repository has been developed to address the specialized needs of the agricultural soil science community, promoting FAIR data publication in the field. Data publications and downloads are steadily increasing. Diverse reuse cases have already demonstrated their added value in addressing pressing challenges in agricultural applications and synthesis. A key insight from analysing data reuse is that it often supports method development and evaluation, driving progress in the field. We believe that the infrastructures, services, and reuse cases described here make a compelling case for the outstanding role disciplinary repositories play in data reusability. We hope to inspire researchers to develop data management plans that include publishing well organized (meta)data collections (such as Weber et al. 2022; Dönmez et al. 2022a, 2022b; Veldkamp et al. 2023) with rich, interoperable metadata in specialized repositories such as the BonaRes Repository. Furthermore, we encourage the use of specialized infrastructures like the Soil Profile Database and the LTE Overview Map, and invite researchers to explore, reuse—and properly cite—published datasets.

Author Contributions

Susanne Lachmuth: formal analysis, data curation, writing – review and editing, visualization, writing – original draft, conceptualization,

methodology. **Cenk Dönmez:** visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing, conceptualization, software, methodology, data curation. **Carsten Hoffmann:** writing – review and editing, writing – original draft, visualization, conceptualization, funding acquisition, methodology, data curation. **Xenia Specka:** visualization, writing – review and editing, writing – original draft, funding acquisition, conceptualization, software, project administration, methodology. **Nikolai Svoboda:** conceptualization, funding acquisition, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing, visualization, data curation, methodology, project administration. **Katharina Helming:** conceptualization, funding acquisition, writing – review and editing, visualization, supervision, project administration, methodology.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data and code supporting this article are available in the BonaRes Repository at <https://doi.org/10.4228/ZALF-VRWF-KC57> (Lachmuth et al. 2025).

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.